

A CONTINUUM DAMAGE MECHANICS MODEL FOR UD COMPOSITES WITH THE EVOLUTION LAW BASED ON THE DAMAGE DRIVING FORCE CONCEPT

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ABSTRACT

The present paper is the implementation of the roadmap as set in [1] with necessary extension, which further develops the previous continuum damage mechanics (CDM) theoretical model for UD composites into a fully functional model in the form of finite element analysis user-defined material subroutine (UMAT). Based on its original capability of modelling matrix cracking damage, the present CDM model benefits from the integration of suitable damage initiation criteria, damage modelling during reloading after unloading and the modelling capability for various abrupt failure modes, making it capable of rationally defining the onset, evolution and orientation of damage under all possible loading conditions while being able to predict abrupt failures like fibre failure.

The application of the CDM model requires a number of suitably defined damage related material properties which are extracted from carefully designed experiments on laminates. To verify the model, applications have been made to quasi-isotropic laminates for which experimental results have been obtained and comparisons are made against the predictions from the CDM modelling.

In the future, this CDM model will be implemented for yarns inside 3D textile composites where it should serve as a necessary material subroutine to be used in the unit cell analysis for textile composites, which will support the data point generation phase in the development of the artificial neural network system for the prediction of textile composite properties as mentioned in [2].

1 INTRODUCTION

In the previous paper [1], the theoretical framework of CDM damage representation and damage evolution for a single array of cracks with common orientation parallel to the fibre direction in a UD composite was derived and presented. The resulting definition of damage driving force led to the construction of damage evolution law and incremental constitutive relationship which are updated in this paper and applied into a damage model in the form of UMAT.

The ultimate result from this work would be a physically rigorous theoretical model that is implemented in finite element analysis for describing the damage initiation, evolution and ultimate failure in UD composites. Once the model is verified by the experiments, it will be applied for modelling the damage in composites with substantially more complex architectures, such as 3D woven and braided composites. For these materials, obtaining theoretical model for damage predictions can be extremely challenging due to an unlimited combination of loading scenarios and variations of geometrical features such as yarn orientations which leads to a more irregular damage profile. Instead, an alternative approach can be used, where the proposed CDM-based model is applied to predict the damage within the yarns, which can be regarded as the UD composites on a micro-scale. Using this yarn damage model as an input for finite element modelling of 3D composites, a neural network as an

interpolation tool to determine 3D composites damaged stiffness can be established based on results from finite element analysis cases.

However, as the starting point for the application and verification of the current CDM model, it was first used for UD plies within laminates and compared against experimental results as illustrated in this paper.

2 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1 Damage initiation criteria & instant failures

In the current CDM damage model, Puck criteria are chosen to be the damage initiation criteria for matrix cracking in UD composites. The reason for this is that Puck criteria were found to be one of the most accurate failure criteria for predicting the failure of UD composites from World Wide Failure Exercise (WWFE). Moreover, Puck criteria used the concept of stress action plane which would be the fracture plane when matrix damage initiated, resulting in an array of fracture planes parallel to the fibre direction for matrix damage with a common orientation determined by stress loadings and material properties. Such a concept is in agreement with the CDM damage representation framework [3] used here since a single array of aligned matrix cracks parallel to fibre direction is assumed to be the form of matrix damage. Therefore, by using Puck criteria, the matrix crack orientation and the onset of matrix damage initiation can be easily determined. With this established, damage representation and damage evolution framework can then be applied to characterise the growth of damage and its effect on UD composite stiffness matrix.

In terms of instant failure modes, fibre failures and compressive failures are the only instant failure modes incorporated. Fibre direction failure criteria from Puck criteria [4] are used in the current model. In particular, the fibre direction compressive failure mode in Puck criteria is fibre kinking which accounted for the contribution from longitudinal shear loading. Once instant fibre failure occurred, E_1 , G_{12} and G_{13} terms in the material stiffness matrix would be reduced to a trivial value in the damage model to represent a complete loss of load-carrying capability for these affected directions.

2.2 Damage driving force and reloading criteria

Recall in [1] the derivation of damage driving force has resulted in three damage driving force components as shown in equation 1 – 3 representing three modes similar to the three classic modes of fracture.

$$\rho_I = P_I \sigma_2^2 \quad (1)$$

$$\rho_{II} = P_{II} \tau_{12}^2 \quad (2)$$

$$\rho_{III} = P_{III} \tau_{23}^2 \quad (3)$$

where

$$P_I = P_I^0 + P_I^1 \omega \quad (4)$$

$$P_{II} = P_{II}^0 + P_{II}^1 \omega \quad (5)$$

$$P_{III} = P_{III}^0 + P_{III}^1 \omega \quad (6)$$

This is also in line with the use of Puck criteria as it specifies only transverse tensile stress, in-plane shear stress and transverse shear stress are the three action loads responsible for creating planar matrix cracks. Therefore after damage initiation identified by Puck criteria, the damage evolution process will be introduced smoothly according to the mode classification matching the action stresses that initiated the cracks.

As introduced in [1], critical damage driving forces were used to devise a mixed-mode criteria to monitor the damage evolution process after damage initiation. The significance of this is to identify if the damage evolution process should continue or not when the damaged material is reloaded after

unloading. The critical driving force values are defined as the driving force values when the damage is about to initiate under one mode of loading and thus they are obtained under σ_2 uniaxial stress state or τ_{12} and τ_{23} pure shear stress states respectively as shown in equation 7 – 9 where S_2 , S_{12} and S_{23} are damage initiation stresses for each loading mode. Therefore, critical driving force values are all material properties specific to the material system used.

$$\rho_I^C = P_I^0 S_2^2 \quad (7)$$

$$\rho_{II}^C = P_{II}^0 S_{12}^2 \quad (8)$$

$$\rho_{III}^C = P_{III}^0 S_{23}^2 \quad (9)$$

A simple mixed-mode reloading criteria using critical driving forces is proposed here as shown in equation 10. Upon reloading of the already damaged material, if the R value exceeds the previous R value registered at the moment of unloading, damage evolution should start again, otherwise damage should not evolve since the severity of loading effect during reloading did not exceed that at the moment of unloading.

$$\frac{\rho_I}{\rho_I^C} + \frac{\rho_{II}}{\rho_{II}^C} + \frac{\rho_{III}}{\rho_{III}^C} = R \quad (10)$$

2.3 Damage evolution law and incremental constitutive relationship

As mentioned in [1], a damage evolution law (equation 11) was proposed to provide a linear relationship between damage increment and damage driving forces, thereby governing the evolution of damage based on stress loadings and existing damage level.

$$\Delta\omega = \mu_I \Delta\rho_I + \mu_{II} \Delta\rho_{II} + \mu_{III} \Delta\rho_{III} \quad (11)$$

where μ_I , μ_{II} and μ_{III} are all material properties specific to the material system used as well.

Expanding above relationship we have:

$$\Delta\omega = \mu_I (\rho_I - \rho_I^0) + \mu_{II} (\rho_{II} - \rho_{II}^0) + \mu_{III} (\rho_{III} - \rho_{III}^0) \quad (12)$$

Substituting equation 1 – 6 into above expression:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta\omega = & \mu_I ((P_I^0 + P_I^1(\omega^0 + \Delta\omega)) (\sigma_2 + \Delta\sigma_2)^2 - (P_I^0 + P_I^1\omega^0) \sigma_2^2) \\ & + \mu_{II} ((P_{II}^0 + P_{II}^1(\omega^0 + \Delta\omega)) (\tau_{12} + \Delta\tau_{12})^2 - (P_{II}^0 + P_{II}^1\omega^0) \tau_{12}^2) \\ & + \mu_{III} ((P_{III}^0 + P_{III}^1(\omega^0 + \Delta\omega)) (\tau_{23} + \Delta\tau_{23})^2 - (P_{III}^0 + P_{III}^1\omega^0) \tau_{23}^2) \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

It is important to note that the incremental stress terms $\Delta\sigma_2$, $\Delta\tau_{12}$ and $\Delta\tau_{23}$ in the above expression are also dependent on incremental damage $\Delta\omega$. For example, in the case of $\Delta\sigma_2$ it can be expressed as the following with stiffness matrix components C^0 and C' as defined previously in [3].

$$\Delta\sigma_2 = \sum_{i=1}^6 (c_{2i}^0 - c_{2i}'(\omega^0 + \Delta\omega)) (\varepsilon_i^0 + \Delta\varepsilon_i) - \sum_{i=1}^6 (c_{2i}^0 - c_{2i}'\omega^0) \varepsilon_i^0 \quad (14)$$

It is obvious that equation 13 is a nonlinear algebraic equation of the damage increment $\Delta\omega$ and to solve $\Delta\omega$ iterative methods can be employed.

With the incremental damage evolution law established, a tangential stiffness matrix can be derived incorporating damage increments to give an incremental constitutive relationship as shown below.

$$\Delta\sigma = (C^0 - C'\omega^0) \Delta\varepsilon - C'(\varepsilon^0 + \Delta\varepsilon) \Delta\omega \quad (15)$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{C}_t &= \frac{\partial \Delta \boldsymbol{\sigma}}{\partial \Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} = (\mathbf{C}^0 - \mathbf{C}' \omega^0) - \mathbf{C}' (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^0 + \Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) \frac{\partial \Delta \omega}{\partial \Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} = (\mathbf{C}^0 - \mathbf{C}' \omega^0) - \mathbf{C}' (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^0 + \Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) \frac{\partial \Delta \omega}{\partial \Delta \boldsymbol{\sigma}} \frac{\partial \Delta \boldsymbol{\sigma}}{\partial \Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} \\
&= (\mathbf{C}^0 - \mathbf{C}' \omega^0) - \mathbf{C}' (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^0 + \Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) \frac{\partial \Delta \omega}{\partial \Delta \boldsymbol{\sigma}} \mathbf{C}_t
\end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

After rearrangement

$$\mathbf{C}_t = \left(\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{C}' (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^0 + \Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) \frac{\partial \Delta \omega}{\partial \Delta \boldsymbol{\sigma}} \right)^{-1} (\mathbf{C}^0 - \mathbf{C}' \omega^0) \tag{17}$$

where I is identity matrix and $\partial \Delta \omega / \partial \Delta \boldsymbol{\sigma}$ can be found using equation 13.

3 IMPEMENTATION INTO ABAQUS UMAT SUBROUTINE

Aforementioned CDM model theoretical framework was coded into a user defined material subroutine (UMAT) for the implicit solver of Abaqus finite element analysis software package. The operation logic of this subroutine is illustrated in the flowchart below.

As can be seen from Figure 1, the subroutine first checks if any instant failure like fibre breakage occurred, then go on to determine whether matrix damage initiated and identify associated damage orientation. If matrix damage was initiated the programme then checks if this is a case of reloading after previous unloading of damaged material and whether the normal stress on the fracture plane is compressive, if all conditions are satisfied, an iterative process for calculating damage increments is entered based on equation 13 - 14 to estimate the damage increment value. If such value is negative, this signifies unloading and the damage increment is artificially set to zero as damage cannot be healed during unloading since damage is irreversible. This will then give a constant total damage value during unloading until next reloading satisfies the mixed-mode reloading criteria equation 10 to trigger damage evolution again. When $\sigma_2 < 0$ (compressive normal stress on the fracture plane), this compressive stress will not contribute to the evolution of cracking normal to its action direction, therefore the corresponding damage driving force increment $\Delta \rho_1$ should be set to zero, while the other two shear stresses should continue to contribute to the damage evolution. Finally, the calculated damage increment is substituted into the tangential stiffness to update stress increments and the entire process is repeated for further strain increments until the end of the finite element analysis.

A 2D plane stress version of this damage model was also created using Matlab so that it can be used for laminate analysis where the effect of degraded ply stiffness due to matrix damage will be accounted for in the laminate ABD matrix. This 2D model also incorporated the 2D stress version of Puck's criteria which serves as the criteria for identifying damage initiation.

Figure 1 Flow chart of CDM model UMAT subroutine

4 VERIFICATION USING LAMINATE TESTS

As the first step to assess the capability of this CDM model, the 2D plane stress version of this CDM model was applied to each UD ply within laminates and a series of quasi-static tests on laminates of IM7/8552 prepreg system were carried out to extract damage related properties. Cross-ply laminates were tested under tension to obtain mode I damage evolution constant μ_I in equation 11 while in-plane shear tests on laminates were for extracting mode II damage evolution constant μ_{II} in equation 11. Since laminates were regarded as in 2D plane stress state in classic laminate analysis and also due to the fact that transverse shear stresses in laminates normally cause inter-ply delamination which is beyond the scope of the current CDM model, mode III transverse shear stress driven damage is ignored here. After the extraction of mode I and mode II damage related properties, these constants were used in the CDM model to predict the stiffness reduction of laminates of different layups with the modelling results verified by experimental result.

4.1 Properties from UD laminates

Basic mechanical properties of the cured UD prepreg were obtained from tensile tests on the IM7/8552 prepreg system UD laminates and the test results were summarised in Table 1.

E_1 (GPa)	E_2 (GPa)	ν_{12}	Longitudinal tensile strength S_1 (MPa)	Transverse tensile strength S_2 (MPa)
188	10.9	0.32	2551	47

Table 1: IM7/8552 UD laminate basic mechanical properties

A typical UD laminate transverse direction tensile stress-strain curve from the tests carried out is shown in Figure 2 and it can be seen that the curve is quite linear up to final fracture of the specimen indicating a rather brittle behaviour and an abrupt catastrophic matrix cracking in the end. Based on this it was envisaged that the transverse tensile strength obtained from this test should be regarded as the damage initiation stress for mode I damage since there is no obvious reduction of transverse elastic modulus before the final failure. Within a laminate, fracture of a 90^0 ply will generally not lead to fracture of the whole laminate as other plies may still be intact. In this case, further loading of the laminate would lead to the generation of more transverse cracks and crack propagation which may finally cause cracks in adjacent plies to join up and cause degradation to laminate stiffness. Such a series of transverse matrix cracking development after damage initiation can then be modelled by the damage evolution part of the current CDM model.

Figure 2 Tensile test result of IM7/8552 UD laminate in transverse direction

4.2 Properties from cross-ply laminates

Tensile tests were done according to ASTM D3039-07 standard on $[0, 90_7]_s$ layup cross-ply laminates to extract μ_I . As mentioned in [1] the ideal method for extracting μ_I and μ_{II} is to plot damage driving force value ρ_I or ρ_{II} against damage variable value ω for each ply when the laminate is gradually loaded and μ_I and μ_{II} can then be determined by calculating the curve slopes according to equation 11. However such an ideal method cannot be applied in reality as to author's knowledge ply stress variation when damage initiated cannot be measured during experiment although ply stress can be calculated using classic laminate theory when the laminate is undamaged. Due to this, a trial and error interpolation method has to be used. The 2D plane stress version CDM model coded in Matlab was then used to interpolate an appropriate μ_I value based on experimental stress-strain curves. Meanwhile, the mode I damage initiation stress 47MPa determined previously was also used in this model to provide the starting point of damage evolution. As can be seen from Figure 3a, the CDM model was able to give a prediction close to the experimental result when using $\mu_I = 6\text{MPa}^{-1}$ with mode I damage initiation stress at 47MPa. With this established, necessary damage related properties for mode I damage prediction are all found.

Figure 3 (a) Cross-ply test result and modelling result; (b) Damage prediction by CDM model for 90^0 plies in the cross-ply laminate

Looking further into the result from the CDM model, the damage prediction for 90^0 plies shown in Figure 3b demonstrated a nonlinear damage value variation trend with the starting point strain matching that of the first plateau on experimental stress-strain curve where transverse matrix cracks started to cause obvious degradation to laminate stiffness. No damage was predicted for the 0^0 plies but Figure 4a showed the predicted stress in 0^0 plies to reach around 2600MPa for final failure which is sensible considering the 2551MPa UD laminate longitudinal strength shown in table 1. The predicted stress in 90^0 plies (Figure 4b) reflected the effect of transverse matrix damage clearly as the plies were gradually unloaded once the damage initiation stress was reached which was then followed by further growth of the damage.

Figure 4 (a) 0° ply and (b) 90° ply stress prediction by CDM model for cross-ply test

4.3 Properties from $\pm 45^\circ$ laminates

In-plane shear test on $[45^\circ, -45^\circ]_{3S}$ laminates were carried out according to ASTM D3518 standard for extracting mode II damage properties. The 0.2% strain offset proof stress value at 53MPa on the experimental stress-strain curve (Figure 5a) was chosen to be the damage initiation point for mode II damage since the material behaviour can be regarded as linear before the proof stress point. Then, repeating the same procedure as described above for mode I damage property determination, a value of 1.1MPa^{-1} was found to be appropriate for μ_{II} which resulted in the CDM model prediction matching closely to experimental result as shown in Figure 5a. However, a point to note is that the stress-strain behaviour obtained from the experiment included shear nonlinearity effect apart from just damage effect. Therefore strictly speaking using only a damage model to obtain the experimental stress-strain behaviour should not be considered as rigorous. Here, for simplicity, all shear nonlinearity effects are represented by the damage model as an approximation.

Figure 5 (a) $\pm 45^\circ$ in-plane shear test result and modelling result; (b) Damage prediction by CDM model for each ply in $\pm 45^\circ$ in-plane shear test

As expected, in terms of damage prediction shown in Figure 5b, the damage started to grow after shear stress in each ply exceeded the mode II damage initiation stress at 53MPa. A closer look at the ply stress plot for fibre direction in Figure 6a revealed that fibre direction stress in each ply was much lower than the UD longitudinal strength which explains why there is no fibre failure found on the specimen after the experiment. On the other hand, ply stress in the transverse direction (Figure 6b) never reached mode I damage initiation stress therefore mode I damage did not appear at all, meaning

only mode II damage occurred during the test. From this in-plane shear test on laminates, all damage related properties for mode II damage were determined.

Figure 6 (a) Fibre direction and (b) Transverse direction ply stress prediction by CDM model for in-plane shear test

4.4 Verification test on quasi-isotropic laminates

With mode I and mode II damage related properties all determined as mentioned above, these were used in the current CDM model to predict the stress-strain behaviour of $[0, 45^{\circ}, -45^{\circ}, 90^{\circ}]_S$ quasi-isotropic (QI) layup laminates under tension. The modelling result is plotted along with the experimental result in Figure 7a which showed a good approximation to the latter. It should be noted that both stress-strain curves in Figure 7a appeared to be quite linear throughout the loading period which seem to indicate that there was no damage to the laminate at all. On the contrary, acoustic emission data obtained during the test proved that there were a lot of cracking events within the laminate throughout the test as shown by the large number of instant energy points registered and the rising accumulated acoustic energy in Figure 7b. Based on this, it can be deduced that although matrix cracking occurred, but the laminate stress-strain curves in Figure 7a remained to be straight due to the high elastic modulus provided by the 0° plies, which effectively "undermined" the effect of matrix damage from other plies, resulting in the overall laminate equivalent modulus appeared to be unaffected. This explanation can be further backed up by looking at Figure 8 where the damage model predicted both $\pm 45^{\circ}$ and 90° plies within the laminate to suffer matrix damage during loading while no damage was predicted by the model for 0° plies.

Figure 7 (a) QI laminate test result and modelling result ; (b) Typical acoustic emission data from QI laminate test

Figure 8 Damage prediction by CDM model for $\pm 45^\circ$ and 90° plies in QI laminate test

To understand why the predicted matrix damage in $\pm 45^\circ$ and 90° plies initiated at different instants during loading, stresses in those plies should be assessed. It can be seen from Figure 9a that stress in 90° plies reached mode I damage initiation stress before 0.6% laminate strain which led to mode I damage growth. In the case of $\pm 45^\circ$ plies as shown in Figure 9b, the damage initiation point was due to a combination of in-plane shear stress and transverse tensile stress in the material axis, therefore $\pm 45^\circ$ plies suffered mixed-mode damage after 0.6% laminate strain as predicted by Puck criteria for damage initiation.

Figure 9 (a) 90° ply and (b) $\pm 45^\circ$ ply stress prediction by CDM model for QI laminate test

4.5 Further verification

Apart from the verification case on QI laminates as shown above, a further verification case was made possible using IM7/8552 laminate test data provided in [5]. Tensile tests on $[0, 90_4]_S$ cross-ply laminates were documented in [5] with extracted test data to give stress-strain curve as shown in Figure 10. Since the same prepreg material system was used, the CDM model was then used to predict the stress-strain behaviour with the exact same properties as defined in the previous QI laminate verification case. The modelling result is satisfactory as shown in Figure 10 where it matched closely to the documented test result from [5]. This proves that as long as the constituent material systems are

the same, the same damage related parameters should be used regardless of the layup sequence because these parameters are indeed ply material properties.

Figure 10 Test result and CDM modelling result for cross-ply laminate tested in [5]

5 CONCLUSIONS

The continuum damage mechanics model for UD composites with the evolution law based on damage driving force developed in [1] was implemented here as a practical damage model for laminates and verified against experimental results. Further work for the development of this damage model is its application to yarns inside textile composites where distribution, orientation and severity of yarn damage are expected to be shown as a part of the finite element unit cell analysis result.

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REFERENCES

- [1] S. Li, T. Yu and Q. Pan, Damage evolution law in the framework of continuum damage mechanics for UD composites, *Proceedings of the 19th International Conference on Composite Materials*, 2013, pp. 354-360
- [2] Q. Pan, S. Li and E. Sitnikova, Strength prediction for textile composites using artificial neural network, principle component analysis and unit cells, *Proceedings of the 20th International Conference on Composite Materials*, 2015
- [3] S. Li, M. Wang, L. Jeanmeur, F. Yu, C. Zhou and Q. Pan, Determination of damage related material constants associated with matrix cracks in UD composites within the continuum damage mechanics framework, submitted for publication to *Composites Sci. Tech.*
- [4] Martin Knops, *Analysis of Failure in Fiber Polymer Laminates: The Theory of Alfred Puck*, Springer, 2008, ISBN: 978-3-540-75764-1
- [5] M. R. Wisnoma, H. H. Toudeshkyb and B. Mohammadic, Experimental and numerical study of oblique transverse cracking in cross-ply laminates under tension, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 67, 2014, pp. 140–148 ([doi:10.1016/j.compositesa.2014.08.004](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2014.08.004)).